

A Study on Job Satisfaction of Private School Teachers with Reference to Mannargudi

Monika G¹, Priyanka R²

¹MBA Student, ²Assistant Professor,

^{1,2}PRIST School of Business, PRIST University, Thanjavur, Tamil Nadu, India

ABSTRACT

The project has been undertaken a study on job satisfaction of teachers working in private school with reference to Mannargudi Thiruvarur (DT).

Job satisfaction refers to the general attitude of employees towards their present job. Job satisfaction probably is the most widely studied variable. Its mainly involved in two variables positive and negative. The person not satisfied his/her work it creates negative attitudes if satisfied it create positive attitudes. So job satisfaction is the most important factor the person involvement to do his or her work. In this research take a teacher were working in different private schools in Mannargudi analysing satisfaction level of his or her work.

KEYWORDS: Job satisfaction

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A. INTRODUCTION

Job satisfaction or employee satisfaction is a measure of workers' contentedness with their job, whether or not they like the job or individual aspects or facets of jobs, such as nature of work or supervision. Job satisfaction can be measured in cognitive (evaluative), affective (or emotional), and behavioral components. Researchers have also noted that job satisfaction measures vary in the extent to which they measure feelings about the job (affective job satisfaction) or cognitions about the job (cognitive job satisfaction). One of the most widely used definitions in organizational research is that of Locke (1976), who defines job satisfaction as "a pleasurable or positive emotional state resulting from the appraisal of one's job or job experiences" (p. 1304). Others have defined it as simply how content an individual is with his or her job; whether he or she likes the job or not. It is assessed at both the global level (whether or not the individual is satisfied with the job overall), or at the facet level (whether or not the individual is satisfied with different aspects of the job). Spector (1997 lists 14 common facets: Appreciation, Communication, Coworkers, Fringe benefits, Job conditions, Nature of the work, Organization, Personal growth, Policies and procedures, Promotion opportunity.

B. Research Methodology

Research ways of doing things is a way to in and organized way solve the research problem it refers not to the research methods but also the logic behind the methods use in the

research study why only particular methods used why certain methods and ways of doing things are not used and so on. Why a research study has been defined, what data has been collected, what method has been adopted and a host of similar questions are usually answered when it is comes to research ways of doing things.

C. RESEARCH DESIGN:

Research design is the basic plan, which guides the collection of related information in a way that's close to truth and money based for the goals for the objectives set up for the project the research design can be classified two types Namely
Descriptive research
Conclusive research

This study is more explanatory in nature, which defines as a research design to plan educated guess potential (related to) possible problems and opportunities present in the decent situation. This study helps to exact the almost defined problem and gives a different way of seeing things (related to) the different (things that changes). More than that, this study establishes (things that are the most important), gain (way of seeing things), identifies different solutions and gather information. In this study of employee's performance judgment. The association of different (things that change) is also decide to some extent here.

Type of Research

Title of research
 Area of research
 Period of research
 Sampling techniques
 Data collection methods
 Tools used for analysis
 Problem Statement
 Limitation on the study

$$\text{Degree of freedom} = (R - 1) \times (C - 1) = (4-1) \times (2-1) = 3$$

The table value of χ^2 for 3 degree of freedom at 5 per cent level of significance is 7.81.

Conclusion:
 Calculated value of chi square is more than the table value, so the null hypothesis is rejected.

SAMPLING DESIGN

Sample design is deciding the sample units, selecting the sample items and deciding the sample size and guess (a number) the universe (typically and expected) from sample data here the (person who works to find information) took 100 sample people who responded of the study.

Data Collection Methods:

PRIMARY DATA

Most important data are believed as the first hand information collected from the people who responded.

The most important data is collected by structured questionnaire.

SECONDARY DATA

The secondary data are collected from the books, magazines, and internet.

Title of the research:

The selected title of the study deal as "A STUDY ON JOB SATISFACTION OF PRIVATE SCHOOL TEACHERS WITH REFERENCE TO MANNARGUDI".

Area of research:

The study is conducted in Mannargudi.

Period of research:

Period of time to collecting data 10 days.

Sampling techniques:

Sample size for the study was selected on the basis of simple random sampling method, 100 employee are randomly selected as sample from different places of Mannargudi.

Questionnaire Design:

Questionnaire contains structured questions and unstructured questions. Structured question involved multiple choice questions and dichotomous question were used to collect the research.

Tools used for analysis:

This part of study is mainly focused on verifying main objective of the study. Researcher used SIMPLE PERCENTAGE ANALYSIS using charts and tables, CHI SQUARE, CORRELATION and ONE WAY ANOVA as statistical tool for analysis of data.

D. Chi Square

Hypothesis:
 Null hypothesis:

There is no relationship between age and the gender respondent's perception towards '
 Calculated value of $\chi^2 = 4.98$

E. ANOVA

Hypothesis:
 Null hypothesis:
 There is no significant ANOVA between education qualification and peaceful working environment in schools.

Conclusion:
 Calculated F value is 0.54 and F significance is 0.46 so calculated value is more than the table value so Null is rejected.

F. CORRELATION:

Calculation value is 0.07633 and so I concluded that there is no significant correlation between job satisfactions of private school teachers.

G. REGRESSION

Null hypothesis:
 There is no significant regression between education qualification and peaceful working environment in schools.

Conclusion:
 Calculated F value is 65.7 and F critical value 3.88 so calculated value is more than the table value so Null is rejected.

FINDINGS

- 63% of the respondents belongs to female class.
- 50% of the respondents are in the age of 21-30yrs.
- 55% of the respondents are PG holders.
- 60% of the respondents are married.
- 50% of the respondents are income 5000-8000 income category.
- 48% of the respondents are accepted to excellent level of job security provided by the management.
- 64% of the respondents are accepted to excellent communication and information flow provided by the management.
- 40% of the respondents are strongly agree to implement skills their jobs.
- 40% of the respondents agree to the management provide peaceful working environment.
- 56% of the respondents are agree to the management put restriction to take leave.
- 52% of the respondents are agree to heavy workload provided by the management.
- 52% of the respondents moderate level of salary provided by the management respected to your experience.
- 48% of the respondents are agree to satisfied training provided by the management.
- 30% of the respondents are strongly agree to never thinking about leaving school.

- 48% of the respondents agree to the management create opportunity for career development.
- 60% of the respondents are agree to interpersonal relationship is good.
- 44% of the respondents moderate level of unfair treatment done by the management.
- 72% of the respondents are accept management to yes option the management provided salary on time.
- 64% of the respondents are accept to yes option the management provide flexible working hour.

Suggestions

- This study is mainly based on the perceptions of the respondents. To solve the problems of the private school teachers in the Mannargudi, the researcher pointed out the following suggestions
- The generation gap brings a lot of changes towards education previously people who went for degree and higher education were very few and they just wanted to have a job. But the present set-up urged the teachers to obtain Master degree plus education training. So they should take necessary steps to continue their higher quality test
- Teachers should be provided with proper guidance and counselling in the organization so that they will be aware of their duties, working conditions in the schools. By knowing this can adjust with the school conditions effectively.

Conclusion

The management should know job dissatisfaction is the most important factor the leads to employee's involvement to work their jobs. So the management take necessary step to take motivate their teachers and convince them to satisfied their work. even they are different type of opinion and expecting different type of facilities we can just take a step to motivating their jobs.

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